

Study on Evaluation Structure of Special Events in Community

– Case Study on “Minoshima Project – Let’s Go Out to Enjoy”

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Abstract

In an attempt to obtain effective guidelines for planning community events, this study examined the structure of rating special events held in communities by taking up “Minoshima Project – Let’s Go Out to Enjoy”, an experiment conducted by the Japanese Ministry of Land, Infrastructure and Transport in Minoshima, Hakata-ku, Fukuoka.

Analysis of visitors’ answers given a questionnaire survey revealed that planning and implementing projects that would enhance six items of evaluation (factor evaluation), “a. events are entertaining”, “b. events are useful to boosts economy in the district”, “e. events are fashionable” and “f. events enhance the unique character of the district”, would improve the value of individual projects, and heighten the comprehensive evaluation of the event in community (MINOSHIMA Project).

Study and analysis of community events and examination of evaluation items (factor evaluation) are believed to delineate the evaluation structure of community events.

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1. Introduction

Special events are being planned and implemented in communities (Note 1) as measures to vitalize the area. There are few data, however, regarding the relation between the rating and the content of an event, and that between the rating of individual events and attractions. As many people participate and work together in such events, the rating would naturally differ depending on whether or not a person evaluating the event is a resident, a participant or a sponsor. Hardly any data concerning such evaluation are available, particularly those concerning visitors.

This study examined the structure of rating a community event in order to obtain effective guidelines for planning community events in future, by taking up “Minoshima Project – Let’s Go Out and Enjoy” (hereinafter Minoshima Project), which was implemented by the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure and Transport in Minoshima, Hakataku, Fukuoka City, and focusing on visitors.

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2. Overview of MINOSHIMA Project

2.1. Outline of Minoshima District

Minoshima district is situated about 1 km south of Hakata railway station (Figure 1), and has served people of Fukuoka as their “kitchen in Hakata” (upper left, Figure 2). The area is currently undergoing developments of many types, particularly of housing (upper right, Figure 2). Hibaruhie Municipal Road divides the district, hindering traffics going to and from south and north (lower left, Figure 2). Two-way traffic passes through the shopping district, creating problems such as high risks of traffic accidents to pedestrians (lower right, Figure 2).

Figure 1: Subject Area

Figure 2: Scenes of Subject Area

2.2. Events and Attractions in Minoshima District

MINOSHIMA Project was implemented between October 14 (Fri) and November 13 (Sun), 2005. Kyushu University, Minoshima Town Council, NPO Hakata Town Promoters, and Association for Promotion of Commercial District in Minoshima deliberated and proposed various events and attractions for MINOSHIMA Project (hereinafter MINOSHIMA Events).

Kyushu University proposed MINOSHIMA Events ① to ⑥ by using two key words: “Market communication”, which attaches importance to communication in kitchens and

markets as an important asset of the community, and the saying “Discover new things by studying the past”, which combines traditional values with new ones to create unique values. MINOSHIMA Events are outlined below.

① BANKO: Temporary wooden benches (BANKO) were placed in the commercial district for people who may want to stop and take rest.

Figure 3: BANKO

② Art Stall: Mobile stalls, etc. were proposed and installed to display art works of students of many vocational colleges for creative works of art located in and around Minoshima.

Figure 4: Art stall

③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet: Visitors were invited to visit 11 food shops in the district and pick up foods for their lunch.

Figure 5: Choosing foods for lunch

④ Outdoor Play Equipment: Children, particularly toddlers, and their parents were invited to visit the space. The purpose was to vitalize the shopping street.

Figure 6: Child playing

⑤ YURARI: Vacant shop space was re-decorated to serve as a resting spot, to supply information about shops in the neighborhood, to hold meetings, to facilitate communication between visitors and shop owners, and to be used as gallery.

Figure 7: Display in YURARI

⑥ Signage: Various signs were posted to optimally guide people to shops.

Figure 8: “Gate Sign” to give information and guide people from and outside Minoshima (to the left), “Connoisseur’s Sign” to show shop owners’ expertise about their merchandise (center), Banners along Minoshima Street to effectively present the atmosphere of the Shopping Area (to the right)

⑦ Open-air Café: Twenty sets of a table and four chairs were placed along the total length (250 m) of the street from south to north.

Figure 9: Visitors enjoying tea

⑧ Rummage Sale: Old clothes and bric-a-brac were collected and sold at the market.

Figure 10: Appearance of sale

⑨ Teahouse: Women's Association served tea and sweets provided by the shops.

Figure 11: Teahouse at night

⑩ Minoshima Tour: Tour of attractive but little known places was held with visitors having their book stamped at each stop.

Figure 12: Child going around the district

3. Questionnaire Survey

3.1. Method

Questionnaire survey was conducted for three days (October 29 (Sat), November 8 (Tue) and 12 (Sat)) during the MINOSHIMA Event by random-sampling visitors, handing out questionnaire sheets, and collecting them after they were filled out.

Figure 13: Survey (left; handing out questionnaire sheets, right; filling in questionnaire sheets)

3.2. Questions

Respondents were asked to evaluate MINOSHIMA Event by using seven-scale SD Method, in which “good” and “not good” were placed at two ends (“Comprehensive Evaluation”).

They were also asked to evaluate each of nine MINOSHIMA Event (except ⑩ One-day Tour) by using the same method (“Individual Evaluation”).

Six factors affecting Individual Evaluation were sampled by referring to past studies and references (Note 2, 3). They are “a: events are entertaining”, “b: events are useful to boost economy in the district”, “c: events bring visitors to the district”, “d: events are novel and unique”, “e: events are fashionable”, and “f: events enhance the unique character of the district”. These factors were evaluated by the seven scale method (7= agree very much ~ 1= do not agree at all) (“Factor Evaluation”).

4. Evaluation of MINOSHIMA Events

4.1. Concept of Evaluation Structure for Community Event

In order to examine how events are evaluated in the district, this study considered the relation among the comprehensive evaluation, the individual evaluation, and the factor evaluation. The comprehensive evaluation is based on the result of the individual evaluation, and the individual evaluation based on factor evaluation (Figure 14)

Thus, it becomes necessary to determine which of MINOSHIMA Events affects the comprehensive evaluation positively. To evaluate the Events individually, it is necessary to

determine which factors affect the individual evaluation positively.

Based on the result of the questionnaire survey, we decided to study the relations.

Figure 14: Structure of Evaluation of Community Event in this Study

4.2. Subjects of Analysis

A total of 238 responses were collected, but only 98 responses which answered all the questions were used for analysis in order to determine the relation between the comprehensive evaluation and the individual evaluation, and that between the individual evaluation and the factor evaluation.

Table 1 shows the breakdown of subjects by gender and age. There were 43 men and 55 women, and 36 in their thirties, followed by 26 in twenties and 13 in fifties. Despite some deviation in age, we divided them into two groups; young people in twenties and younger (singles and small families) were considered not to be closely involved with the District, and middle and elderly people in thirties and older (mostly families) were considered to be closely involved with shops.

Table1 : Breakdown of Subjects for Analysis

	Young group			Middle age and elderly group					Total
	≤ 14	15-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	$70 \geq$	
Men	-	4	11	10	6	7	4	1	43
Women	1	4	11	26	2	6	1	-	55
Total	1	8	26	36	8	13	5	1	98
		35				63			

4.3. Relationship between Comprehensive Evaluation and Individual Evaluation

4.3.1. Simple Calculation

Figure 15 shows results of the comprehensive and the individual evaluations broken down by genders, and Figure 16 the result of the comprehensive and the individual evaluations broken down by age groups. The comprehensive evaluation for MINOSHIMA Events was slightly below “2 = quite good” in both results, and may be rated as good.

Individual evaluations for the respective Events, on the other hand, were varied. Evaluations by women and Young Group were higher. All the groups rated “③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet” and “⑤ YURARI” high; there were hardly any variation by gender or age for “③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet”. “⑧ Rummage Sale” got very poor rating.

Figure 15: Comprehensive evaluation and individual evaluation broken down by genders

Figure 16: Comprehensive evaluation and individual evaluation broken down by age groups

4.3.2. Multiple Regression Analysis

We then conducted t-test (1% point) on the means of comprehensive and individual evaluations broken down by genders and age groups. There were no significant differences.

Results of 98 responses were subjected to multiple regression analysis by deeming the comprehensive evaluation as a dependent variable and the individual evaluation as an independent variable. As shown in Table 2, the multiple correlation coefficient was $R = 0.580$, and the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.336$. Both coefficients were small and did not fit the multiple regression formula shown at the bottom of Table 2, but four events of ⑦ Open-air Café, ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet, ⑥ Signage, and ④ Outdoor Play Equipment were found to affect the comprehensive evaluation positively and ⑨ Teahouse negatively.

Table 2: Result of Multiple Regression Analysis of Comprehensive and Individual Evaluations

	Comprehensive Evaluation
Multiple regression coefficient R	0.580
Coefficient of determination R^2	0.336
Partial regression coefficient (constant)	2.043
① BANKO	0.014
② Art Stalls	0.078
③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet	0.270
④ Outdoor Play Equipment	0.153
⑤ YURARI	-0.060
⑥ Signage	0.175
⑦ Open-air Café	0.294
⑧ Rummage Sale	-0.066
⑨ Teahouse	-0.193

4.4. Relation between Individual Evaluation and Factor Evaluation

4.4.1. Simple Calculation

The factor evaluation was conducted in respect of four events of ⑦ Open-air Café, ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet, ⑥ Signage and ④ Outdoor Play Equipment by examining genders and age groups.

⑦ Open-air Café

Figure 17 shows the result of factor analysis by genders and Figure 18 the result of factor analysis by age groups.

Evaluation score by women and young group was high, and “c. events bring visitors to the district” and ”a. events are entertaining” were evaluated highly by both groups, and “e. events are fashionable” was rated low.

Figure 17: Factor Evaluation by Gender of ⑦ Open-air Café

Figure 18: Factor Evaluation by Age Group of ⑦ Open-air Café

③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet

Figure 19 shows the result of the factor evaluation by genders and Figure 20 the result of the factor evaluation by age groups.

Result by gender showed hardly any difference, but the event was highly evaluated by the younger group.

It was evaluated highly (above 6 points) by both genders and age groups in respect of all the factors except “e. events are fashionable”.

Figure 19: Factor Evaluation by Gender of ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet

Figure 20: Factor Evaluation by Age Group of ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet

⑥ Signage

Figure 21 shows the result of factor evaluation by genders and Figure 22 the result by age groups. This was evaluated highly by women and younger group. Each factor was evaluated evenly by genders and age groups.

Figure 21: Factor evaluation by gender of ⑥ Signage

Figure 22: Factor evaluation by age group of ⑥ Signage

④ Outdoor Play Equipment

Figure 23 shows the result of factor evaluation by genders and Figure 24 the result by age groups. Women and younger group evaluated Outdoor Play Equipment highly by citing “a. events are entertaining” and “c. events bring visitors to the district”, but their rating on “e. events are fashionable” was low.

Figure 23: Factor Evaluations by Genders for ④ Outdoor Play Equipment

Figure 24: Factor Evaluations by Age Groups for ④ Outdoor Play Equipment

4.4.2. Multiple Regression Analysis

We then conducted t-test (1% point) on the means of factor evaluation broken down by genders and age groups. There were no significant differences.

Ninety-eight responses were then subjected to multiple regression analysis to determine which factor positively affected the individual evaluation of four MINOSHIMA Events, that affected the comprehensive evaluation positively.

As shown in Table 3, the multiple correlation coefficient R was 0.664 and the coefficient of

determination R^2 0.417 for ⑦ Open-air Café; the multiple correlation coefficient R was 0.683 and the coefficient of determination R^2 0.466 for ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet; the multiple correlation coefficient R was 0.627 and the coefficient of determination R^2 0.393 for ⑥ Signage; the multiple correlation coefficient R was 0.548 and the coefficient of determination R^2 0.300 for ④ Outdoor Play Equipment. Both coefficients were small and did not fit the multiple regression formula shown at the bottom of Table 3, but the two factors were found to positively affect the individual evaluation; for ⑦ Open-air Café and ③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet. They were “a. events are entertaining” and “c. events bring visitors to the district”. For ⑥ Signage, they were “b. events are useful to boost economy in the district”. For ④ Outdoor Play Equipment, three factors of “a. events are entertaining”, “f. events enhance the unique character of the district”, and “e. events are fashionable” were found to have affected the positive individual evaluation.

When these results were compared in respect of four MINOSHIMA Events, the factors of “a. events are entertaining”, “b. events are useful to boosts economy in the district”, “e. events are fashionable”, “f. events enhance the unique character of the district” were found to positively affect the evaluations allowing some differences in degrees. On the other hand, the item “c. events bring visitors to the district” affected “④ Outdoor Play Equipment negatively, suggesting that the content of events did not affect the evaluation in a stable manner.

Table 3: Results of multiple regression analysis of individual evaluation and factor evaluation

	⑦ Open-air Café	③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet	⑥ Signage	④ Outdoor Play Equipment
Multiple regression coefficient R	0.646	0.683	0.627	0.548
Coefficient of determination R^2	0.417	0.466	0.393	0.300
Partial regression coefficient (constant)	1.724	1.684	1.974	2.251
a. events are entertaining	0.257	0.545	0.100	0.413
b. events are useful to boost economy in the district	0.106	0.109	0.270	0.057
c. events bring visitors to the district	0.212	0.181	-0.014	-0.194
d. events are novel and unique	0.066	-0.052	0.126	-0.084
e. events are fashionable	-0.043	-0.052	0.107	0.159
f. events enhance the unique character of the district	0.115	-0.004	0.047	0.206

Relevance of the factor evaluation and four MINOSHIMA Events is examined. “⑦ Open- air Café”, “③ Minoshima Lunch Buffet” and “④ Outdoor Play Equipment” were evaluated as being “a. events are entertaining” in that the visitors actually could enjoy them by participating in these events rather than just observing them. “⑥ Signage”, which was relevant to “b. events are useful to boost economy in the district”, was evaluated highly useful for economy because its installation increased the number of visitors by serving as a precise guide for shops in the district and achieving effectiveness in presentation. “④ Outdoor Play Equipment”, which was evaluated as being relevant to the factors “e. events are fashionable” and “f. events enhance the unique character of the district”, was considered interesting and cute to look at and unique by visitors and to be utilizing the place where it was installed.

4.5. Relation of Comprehensive Evaluation, Individual Evaluation and Factor Evaluation

As discussed above, the factors that differed depending on the type of events and affected the individual evaluation stably were “a. events are entertaining”, “b. events are useful to boost economy in the district”, “e. events are fashionable” and “f. events enhance the unique character of the district”.

This finding suggests the need to plan and implement events and attractions that would improve evaluation of these factors to thereby improve the comprehensive evaluation of the community events.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the evaluation structure of community events by taking up an example of MINOSHIMA Project. Planning and implementing the events and attractions by considering the factors of “entertaining”, “economy”, “fashionableness”, and “regional character” led to their high evaluation, and obtained desirable guidelines.

We believe that investigations and analyses of events of different regions and further study of factors will more clearly define the evaluation structure of community events.

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References and Notes

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Community events means events implemented by the constituting members (inhabitants) of local autonomous bodies or local communities. Many of such events are sponsored or supported by administrative organs such as prefectural and municipal governments, and the executive committees representing public and quasi-public organizations of the community (Chamber of Commerce and Industry, etc.)

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